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69 **Running title:** EEG in epilepsy research

70 **Keywords:** EEG, animal models, seizures, epilepsy, interictal activity, comorbidities,

71 high-frequency oscillations, genetic epilepsies, analysis

72

73 **Number of words abstract:** 257

74 **Number of words in main text:** 6434

75 **Number of references:** 232

76 **Abstract**

77 Electroencephalography (EEG) has been instrumental in epilepsy research for the past
78 century, both for basic and translational studies. Its contributions have advanced our
79 understanding of epilepsy, shedding light on the pathophysiology and functional
80 organization of epileptic networks, and mechanisms underlying seizures. Here we re-
81 examine the historical significance, ongoing relevance, and future trajectories of EEG
82 in epilepsy research. We describe traditional approaches to record brain electrical
83 activity and discuss novel cutting-edge large-scale techniques using micro-electrode
84 arrays. Contemporary EEG studies explore brain potentials beyond the traditional
85 Berger frequencies to uncover yet underexplored mechanisms operating at ultra-slow
86 and high frequencies which have been proven valuable in understanding the principles
87 of ictogenesis, epileptogenesis, and endogenous epileptogenicity. Integrating EEG
88 with modern techniques such as optogenetics, chemogenetics, and imaging provides
89 a more comprehensive understanding of epilepsy. EEG has become an integral
90 element in a powerful suite of tools for capturing epileptic network dynamics across
91 various temporal and spatial scales, ranging from rapid pathological synchronization
92 to the long-term processes of epileptogenesis or seizure cycles. Advancements in EEG
93 recording techniques parallel the application of sophisticated mathematical analyses
94 and algorithms, significantly augmenting the information yield of EEG recordings.
95 Beyond seizures and interictal activity, EEG has been instrumental in elucidating the
96 mechanisms underlying epilepsy-related cognitive deficits and comorbidities. While
97 EEG remains a cornerstone in research, persistent challenges such as limited spatial
98 resolution, artifacts, and the difficulty of long-term recording highlight the ongoing need
99 for refinement. Despite these challenges, EEG continues to be a fundamental research
100 tool, playing a central role in unraveling disease mechanisms and drug discovery.

101 **Key points**

- 102 • EEG was, is, and will be a fundamental tool in basic and translational epilepsy
103 research.
- 104 • The EEG in animal models provides useful information that expands well
105 beyond seizure detection.
- 106 • The application of EEG techniques to humans will expand due to rapid
107 advances in material, hardware, and software technology.
- 108 • EEG alone or combined with imaging, optogenetics, and other modern research
109 tools became a powerful technique for dissecting the cellular and network
110 mechanisms of epilepsies.
- 111 • Artificial intelligence in EEG analyses, if used in a manner that is validated by
112 expert EEG readers, can potentially increase its information yield.

113 **1. Introduction**

114 Electroencephalography (EEG) has been a key research technique since the
115 inception of epilepsy research more than a century ago. The first records of utilizing
116 recording of brain electrical activity date to the end of the 19th and the middle of the
117 20th century^{1,2}. With technological advancements in amplifier design, followed by
118 digitization and the utilization of computer analysis, the information extracted from EEG
119 recordings expanded very rapidly. These advances rendered EEG a valuable tool in
120 experimental and clinical epileptology. Throughout this review, we use the term EEG
121 to refer to local field potential (LFP) as well as EEG. However, we recognize that they
122 are not the same.

123 Since the early studies, a dichotomy in experimental and clinical EEG recording
124 has occurred. While clinical EEG often captures traditional Berger's frequency bands,
125 experimental research expanded to recordings of brain activities over wide frequency
126 bands ranging from ultra-slow³ to very high frequencies of oscillations⁴⁻⁶. It should be
127 noted, however, that aperiodic or non-rhythmic patterns are also important aspects of
128 the EEG, and that they may influence the interpretation of oscillatory (periodic)
129 signals⁷. Later, new electrode designs were introduced into research including the
130 implementation of multichannel recording^{8,9} that started to provide more complex
131 information about the spatial topography of epileptiform activity and seizures¹⁰. The
132 introduction of new materials and state-of-the-art technologies contributed to the
133 development of new electrodes (injectable, dissolvable, foldable) with integrated
134 circuits that allow for chronic recording of multichannel population activity combined
135 with recording activity from individual neurons¹⁰. Modern epilepsy research utilizes
136 recording techniques that can provide highly complex information about brain

137 dynamics at multiple temporal and spatial scales (discussed below). The introduction
138 of computers represented a crucial step in epilepsy research. Mathematical analyses
139 of EEG signals dramatically increased the information yield far beyond the visual
140 inspection and became an integral part of brain research. Analytical tools such as
141 advanced machine learning toolboxes brought detailed information about the epileptic
142 network organization, synchronization mechanisms, and underlying dynamical
143 processes^{11,12}.

144 The electrographic phenomena recorded in the epileptic brain are considered a
145 hallmark epilepsy¹³. For instance, these phenomena include various forms of interictal
146 epileptiform discharges (IEDs), high-frequency oscillations (HFOs), and other events
147 such as delta brush patterns. EEG studies brought significant insights into the cellular
148 and network mechanisms of epileptogenesis¹⁴⁻¹⁶, ictogenesis^{17,18}, functional
149 organization of epileptogenic tissues¹⁹, and comorbidities^{20,21}. Historically, seizures
150 and IEDs represent key phenomena that pinpoint the presence and activity of epileptic
151 neurons^{13,22}. The introduction of new research techniques such as *in vivo* imaging,
152 optogenetics, and chemogenetics provide novel information about cellular, metabolic,
153 or vascular contributors to epilepsy. These techniques are often implemented in
154 combination with EEG, and observed phenomena are typically interpreted with respect
155 to the traditional electrographic hallmarks of epilepsy.

156 In epilepsy research, EEG is typically recorded in small animals (mainly in
157 rodents) using electrodes with diameters ranging from a few micrometers to dozens of
158 micrometers. In humans, this would correspond to micro-EEG^{23,24}. Several types of
159 electrodes can be used to record population activity from individual neurons residing
160 in the vicinity of the electrode as well as extracellular field potentials produced by many
161 neurons, the so-called LFP^{9,25}.

162 **2. What the EEG can tell us about the brain**

163 Various active neuronal (cellular) processes generate electrical currents across
164 the cellular membranes. The superimposition of these membrane currents in the
165 extracellular space generates an electric field that can be recorded with extracellularly
166 positioned electrodes²⁵⁻²⁷. The major source of EEG is synaptic activity on the
167 dendrites of pyramidal cells. Indeed, when a group of neurons are synchronously
168 activated, the summation of extracellular currents gives rise to electric fields, which can
169 be detectable on the EEG²⁵. Both excitatory and inhibitory postsynaptic currents
170 contribute to EEG signal, where morphology, amplitude, and duration of EEG
171 waveforms depend on factors including but not limited to the number of activated
172 synapses, the number of synchronously activated neurons, and electric field
173 orientation with respect to the electrode^{6,26,27}. Physiological cellular processes involved
174 in functions like cognition, memory formation, or sleep generate coordinated neuronal
175 activity and membrane potential changes that contribute to information processing and
176 manifest in extracellular recording as electric field fluctuation and various rhythms or
177 oscillations²⁸⁻³². In epilepsy, the synchronous synaptic activity of large neuronal
178 ensembles and membrane depolarization (e.g., giant excitatory postsynaptic potentials
179 or paroxysmal depolarizing shifts) with strong transmembrane currents manifest as
180 interictal or ictal epileptiform discharges of various morphologies^{13,33,34}. Interictally, the
181 transient excitation is curtailed by subsequent inhibition that correlates with a slow
182 wave on the EEG. The cellular and network mechanisms revealed by the study of EEG
183 signals are rich and beyond the scope of this manuscript^{13,35-38}. Apart from excitatory
184 and inhibitory synaptic activity, other cellular activities contribute to EEG. Large
185 synchronous neuronal depolarizations due to the opening of voltage-gated channels
186 create depolarizing envelopes (e.g., a burst of action potential riding on dendritic

187 calcium spikes) and massive transmembrane currents as well as synchronous spike-
188 induced after-hyperpolarizations due to potassium channel opening^{25,39-41}.
189 Extracellular correlates of action potentials of individual cells (single-unit activity) or
190 multiple cells (multi-unit activity) can be recorded with special electrodes⁹. Due to their
191 short duration (<1 ms), neuronal action potential firing can be recorded in LFP under
192 conditions of very high synchrony. Synchronous action potential (spontaneous or
193 stimulation-induced) firing manifests in EEG as a deflection designated as population
194 spikes lasting a few milliseconds that can be observed during seizures or interictal
195 states where they manifest as HFOs - an episode of repeated population spikes^{22,42-}
196 ⁴⁶. In the majority of cases, extracellular field potentials are generated by pyramidal
197 cells (i.e., layer 5 pyramidal cells)⁴⁷. Interneurons contribute to EEG signals largely
198 indirectly through the inhibitory post-synaptic currents generated on the principal cells
199 or through the modulation of principal cell excitability. However, it should be noted that
200 interneurons can exert a similar contribution to the EEG as big pyramidal cells⁴⁸. For
201 instance, hilar interneurons directly contribute to the generation of distinct EEG events
202 such as the dentate spike⁴⁹. Moreover, inhibition mediated by interneurons can
203 orchestrate important functional roles related to memory⁵⁰ and place cell formation⁵¹ in
204 the hippocampus. In the context of epilepsy models, several experimental preparations
205 have described IEDs generated by the prominent activation of interneurons^{37,52}. Glial
206 cells also influence EEG signals indirectly, apart from ultra-slow potentials and direct
207 current (DC) potentials, where glial depolarization can contribute directly to EEG
208 genesis.

209 DC potential, ultra-slow, or steady potentials refer to a wide frequency range of
210 brain activities (<0.5 Hz) that are recorded under physiological and pathological
211 conditions. While experimental studies pay attention to DC recording, DC potentials

212 were neglected in clinical studies for a long time⁶. However, it should be noted that
213 ultra-slow or DC recordings require specialized equipment such as DC amplifiers and
214 non-polarizing electrodes⁵³⁻⁵⁵. DC potentials comprise slow and faster activities
215 corresponding to fast potential fluctuations on EEG. Several pathological activities, like
216 seizure-related DC shifts or spreading depolarization, manifest as dramatic changes
217 in DC potential⁵⁶. DC potentials reflect long-lasting neuronal and glial depolarizations,
218 which generate large transmembrane currents and are accompanied by significant
219 changes in extracellular potassium⁵⁷ and calcium⁵⁸ concentration. The DC potentials
220 and EEG activity provide comprehensive information about the cellular and network
221 processes that can't be solely derived from recording traditional EEG activity *per se*⁵⁹.

222 Because intracellular studies are often difficult to conduct, extracellular
223 recordings have been valuable in allowing interrogation of a myriad of neuronal and
224 non-neuronal processes, ranging from cellular firing to network activity at a local or
225 global brain level. However, it should be noted that intracellular approaches have
226 become feasible even in freely moving rodents⁶⁰. Such novel approaches may
227 significantly expand the use of intracellular approaches that historically have been
228 instrumental in providing direct cellular evidence of the potential origins of EEG waves,
229 including in epilepsy research.⁶¹

230 Several processes relevant to epilepsy can be studied at the sub-millisecond
231 temporal scale^{35,62}, but also at the temporal scale of weeks, months, and over a wide
232 frequency band^{15,16,63,64}. This makes EEG a very powerful tool to explore the epileptic
233 brains. With EEG, fast processes like ictal synchronization, HFO genesis, and cellular
234 firing during populational activities can be studied with high temporal precision^{35,62}. On
235 the other hand, EEG is an effective tool for studying network reorganization and brain

236 dynamics during epileptogenesis, disease progression, seizure cycles, and response
237 to treatment^{15,65-67}.

238 Multimodal recording of preclinical and clinical EEG combined with other
239 modalities such as electrocardiogram (ECG), respiration, or electromyogram (EMG) is
240 instrumental in studying the systemic impact of epileptic activity on cardiovascular,
241 autonomic, respiratory, and motor functions. For instance, the multimodal recording,
242 combined with DC recordings, is critical in preclinical studies of sudden unexpected
243 death in epilepsy (SUDEP; ^{68,69}), where this methodology has brought seminal insights
244 that disclose the relationship between seizures, spreading depolarization, postictal
245 depression, and their role in ictal apnoea, terminal respiratory arrest, or seizure-related
246 cardiovascular abnormalities.

247 Animal EEG studies always played a key role in pharmacological research and
248 drug discovery. Seizures represent the primary major symptom of epilepsy. Currently,
249 EEG can provide the most accurate information about the actual number of seizures,
250 even though its accuracy still depends upon the number and spatial arrangement of
251 the used electrodes and the type of seizures⁷⁰ (focal aware, focal with impaired
252 awareness, generalized). Many seizures can be electrographic-only or accompanied
253 by subtle changes in animal behavior that cannot be detected by visual review of video
254 recordings^{65,66}. Similarly, humans can report only a few seizures, while hundreds of
255 electrographic seizures can be identified in EEG with patients not being aware of
256 them⁷¹. The efficacy of new drugs or new therapies (e.g., gene therapy, gene
257 modulation, neurostimulation) is determined by their efficacy in reducing or completely
258 abolishing seizures, and thus the EEG represents one of the most optimal methods to
259 measure therapeutic efficacy⁷²⁻⁷⁵. A limitation is, however, that the customary EEG
260 studies cannot survey the whole brain and, as a result, some very focal seizures may

261 still remain undetected with the surface EEG requiring more extensive probing with
262 targeted depth EEG electrodes.

263 Overall, electrophysiological tools enable us to explore brain function at a wide
264 range of spatial and temporal scales (**Figure 1**) and over a wide range of frequencies,
265 from DC shifts and ultra-slow fluctuations to high-frequency activities up to several kHz.
266 Therefore, the recording of extracellular activities can provide a quite comprehensive
267 profile of epileptic processes and underlying disease mechanisms.

268

269 **3. The role of EEG in comorbidities**

270 Besides epileptic activity, EEG is used to explore, characterize, and monitor
271 physiological or pathological brain signals, activities, or states like sleep or
272 wakefulness, all of which can directly or indirectly affect cognitive function. Indeed,
273 EEG and extracellular recordings help to disclose neuronal network mechanisms or
274 EEG signals associated with memory and cognitive deficits accompanying epilepsy.
275 For example, various brain oscillations (i.e., theta, alpha, beta, gamma, ripples) may,
276 in certain instances, represent electrographic correlates of highly orchestrated network
277 activity which are instrumental for cognitive function³². Alterations of these rhythms
278 have been described in many experimental models of disease, but a potential link to
279 epilepsy-related comorbidities requires caution and consideration of the brain area
280 under investigation and behavioral state investigated⁷⁶⁻⁸¹. For example, there are
281 certain brain regions such as the hippocampus⁸² that inherently shows quite robust
282 oscillations compared to other structures. In this context, brain atlases⁸³ describing the
283 distribution of EEG activities or oscillations are valuable to differentiate normal from
284 abnormal EEG rhythms^{80,84}. Moreover, it should be noted that temporal coordination is

285 another critical aspect of brain communication that can be affected in epilepsy and thus
286 contribute to cognitive deficits (for a review, see reference⁸⁵).

287 Alterations in cognitive processes can manifest in EEG as a loss of physiological
288 oscillations or changes in their properties, like changes in the frequency or amplitude
289 of the oscillation⁸⁶⁻⁸⁸. In this context, epileptiform activity is known to disrupt normal
290 oscillations such as those occurring in theta frequency^{89,90}. Sporadic epileptiform
291 activity can impact neuronal processing locally but also in remote areas where it
292 propagates. Indeed, IEDs can exert widespread effects during non-rapid eye
293 movement sleep⁹¹, that appear to disrupt large-scale cortico-cortical coupling
294 necessary for normal brain development and cognitive function⁹².

295 The occurrence of IEDs during a cognitive task can disrupt memory in rats⁹³ as
296 well as humans⁹⁴. Moreover, the frequency of IEDs can predict the degree of
297 neuropsychological impairment. As an example, generalized IED frequency is
298 inversely correlated with performance on generalized intelligence tests and academic
299 performance^{95,96}. Children with idiopathic generalized epilepsies who present with
300 IEDs have deficits in processing speed, attention, visuospatial function, and
301 arithmetic⁹⁷. Moreover, focal IEDs relate to anatomically specific dysfunction^{98,99}. Scalp
302 EEG and intracranial EEG recordings during continuous cognitive tasks can quantify
303 the dynamic disruption of IEDs. In 1939, Schwab first noticed that “subclinical EEG
304 discharges” slowed reaction time or impaired stimulus response, an electroclinical
305 phenomenon now referred to as transient cognitive impairment¹⁰⁰. Of interest,
306 cognitive activity can either facilitate^{100,101} or suppress IED frequency¹⁰². Aarts et al.
307 were the first to demonstrate the spatial specificity of focal IEDs. They showed that left-
308 lateralized IEDs during verbal information processing were associated with increased
309 error rate, while right-lateralized IEDs affected non-verbal learning¹⁰⁰. Intracranial EEG

310 has permitted a more anatomically precise understanding of how IEDs can disrupt
311 specific cognitive functions. For example, IEDs affecting the lateral frontotemporal
312 cortex prolong reaction time during auditory naming tasks and decrease word
313 repetition speed, suggesting that they contribute to the common cognitive complaint of
314 word-finding difficulty¹⁰³. IEDs occurring in the left mesial temporal, lateral temporal
315 neocortical, and fusiform gyrus regions during encoding, and outside the seizure onset
316 zone (SOZ), reduce the odds of verbal retrieval¹⁰⁴ by as much as 15% per event.
317 Likewise, hippocampal IEDs occurring outside the SOZ during the encoding and
318 retrieval phase of a face-profession association task reduce the odds of remembering
319 by 15% and 25%, respectively¹⁰⁵, by putatively decreasing sharp-wave ripple (SPW-
320 R) frequency. Indeed, hippocampal IEDs during sleep compete with SPW-Rs, hijacking
321 normal physiological consolidation processes and thereby disrupting memory
322 consolidation¹⁰⁶.

323 Underlying disease mechanisms and epilepsy-related structural (e.g., cell loss,
324 synaptic reorganization) and functional (e.g., neurotransmission, excitability, firing
325 properties) changes may interfere with physiological network activity and neural
326 processing leading to various forms of neuropsychiatric comorbidities – intellectual
327 disability, memory decline, and autistic phenotype¹⁰⁷. Notably, antiseizure medications
328 can have a similar impact on physiological brain functions^{108,109}.

329 The EEG is also important in addressing reasons underlying comorbidities in
330 brain disorders that share commonalities with epilepsy, such as Alzheimer's disease
331 (AD). For instance, patients with AD present with epileptiform activity^{110,111} like patients
332 with epilepsy, and they also share rhythmopathies of gamma and ripple oscillations,
333 as demonstrated in animal models^{46,79,112-116}. The presence of epileptiform activity and
334 rhythmopathies on EEG has been associated with impaired cognition in both AD

335 patients and animal models^{110,112,113,115}. In this regard, anti-seizure medications can be
336 beneficial in patients with epileptiform activity on their EEGs¹¹⁷. Seizures can also
337 occur in AD¹¹⁸ where they further exacerbate cognitive impairment¹¹⁹. HFOs such as
338 those recorded in the context of epilepsy are another EEG abnormality that has been
339 reported to occur in several AD mouse lines⁴⁶ although their role in impaired memory
340 in AD remains unknown. Nevertheless, selective disruption of HFOs in epilepsy using
341 closed-loop optogenetics restores memory¹²⁰ in line with previous findings showing
342 that pharmacological normalization of abnormal cell firing underlying HFOs can
343 improve memory recall in epileptic rats¹¹⁶.

344 Taken together, the EEG and other electrophysiological techniques are highly
345 instrumental in providing insight into the mechanisms of how epilepsy and other brain
346 disorders that share common EEG disturbances with epilepsy affect cognitive
347 processes^{86,87}. Moreover, the EEG represents an effective tool to monitor the impact
348 of treatments for seizures and epileptiform activity on cognitive functions thereby
349 disclosing possible mechanisms underlying the beneficial effects of treatments on
350 functional outcomes.

351

352 **4. Traditional and new EEG recording methods**

353 The methods of EEG recording in animals became more sophisticated with
354 technological development (**Figure 2**). Over the last decade, we observed a rapid
355 expansion of advanced methods that allow for a long-term, multi-site recording of LFPs
356 combined with the recording of unit activity that can provide detailed information about
357 neuronal processes simultaneously occurring across multiple temporal and spatial
358 domains¹⁰. Modern epilepsy research benefits from a large portfolio of recording

359 methods ranging from a simple single EEG electrode to hundreds of EEG channels.
360 Nevertheless, it should be noted that traditional EEG recordings are very often used to
361 validate emerging methods since they are considered the gold standard in the EEG
362 research arena.

363 The main principles of traditional animal EEG recording, combined with video
364 monitoring, have been repeatedly described and discussed¹²¹⁻¹²³. However, the most
365 important considerations for selecting the appropriate EEG recording techniques are
366 largely based on the research questions and hypotheses we aim to address. One of
367 the first considerations regarding implantation pertains to brain areas of interest.
368 Superficial structures such as the cerebral cortex can be recorded using screw
369 electrodes and modern electrocorticographic (ECoG) arrays, whereas deeper
370 structures typically require intracranial approaches using depth electrodes of different
371 sizes, microwires, or micro-machined electrode assemblies, such as silicon probes. In
372 this context, the choice of wires vs. silicon probes largely depends on the spatial
373 resolution one wants to achieve and the budget, because silicon probes are typically
374 more expensive.

375 Two of the most common approaches to record video-EEG include tethered and
376 radiotelemetry approaches¹²¹. Tethered approaches utilize wires that are attached to
377 the subject being recorded, allowing nearly continuous recording over long periods of
378 time (typically several weeks). Although tethered approaches may restrict the
379 movement of the animal, the use of motorized commutators mitigates this effect. Also,
380 during tethered recordings, animals are typically single-housed to minimize cable
381 entangling as animals move in the recording chamber, dislodging of the headmounts,
382 or masking an animal's behavior by the cage mate during a target event. However,
383 tethered recordings can limit the ability to interact with littermates socially. In the

384 context of epilepsy, this aspect is of high relevance because single housing has been
385 associated with increased seizure burden¹²⁴. In this context, telemetry can be
386 advantageous because animal movement is less restrictive compared to tethered
387 approaches. Nowadays, implanted telemetry transmitters have small sizes and record
388 signals from multiple channels at high sampling rates and of various modalities. Even
389 multiple animals with implanted telemetric devices can be housed and recorded
390 together¹²⁵. Some of the restrictions of telemetry include limited battery life, often
391 limited recording bandwidth, and capacity for much fewer electrodes vs. tethered
392 recordings. Nevertheless, some newer developments offer the possibility of wireless
393 charging for telemetry transmitters through inductive charge^{126,127}. Other approaches
394 do not require the use of batteries during recording¹²⁸. Moreover, in some cases,
395 telemetry devices can be placed on a head mount, making batteries more accessible
396 and easier to replace compared to implantable transmitters. Indeed, this approach has
397 been implemented in seizure monitoring experiments performed in primates¹²⁹. Other
398 limitations of telemetry are related to the risk of masking animal behaviors from cage
399 mates, signal interruptions or artifacts from cage mates, high cost, and reusability of
400 implants.

401 In animal models of seizures and epilepsy, advanced electrophysiological
402 methods have been applied to better target mechanisms and circuits involved, aided
403 by the use of Neuropixel probes¹³⁰, silicon probe arrays¹³¹⁻¹³⁵, and tetrodes^{136,137}.
404 Inspired by this data, these tools have been incorporated into human brain recordings
405 (**Table 1**). They permit assessing both LFP and unit activity at different temporal and
406 spatial resolutions, which have significantly expanded our understanding of the
407 mechanistic complexities surrounding human brain pathological activity from the
408 cellular level and local networks nearly to whole brain phenomena. In an effort to utilize

409 methods and terms that allow reliable comparison between studies, a series of
410 common data elements (CDEs) have been developed to assist epilepsy
411 researchers^{138,139}. These CDEs are highly useful for experienced neurophysiologists
412 as well as for scientists who would like to introduce EEG into their methodological
413 portfolio.

414 EEG can also be combined with other methods that are currently used in
415 neuroscience research to increase the yield of information and to dissect cellular and
416 network mechanisms of epileptic activity, including seizures. Thus, EEG can be
417 combined with optogenetic stimulation or inhibition to better understand the
418 contribution of different cell types to EEG activity. Optogenetics allows cell-type-
419 specific control of cellular activity through light delivery. Essentially, the approach
420 requires the expression of genetically engineered light-sensitive ion channels or pumps
421 in a tissue of interest and optical control through a light source¹⁴⁰. In the context of
422 epilepsy, optogenetic stimulation or inhibition has been deemed a valuable approach
423 to dissecting the role of individual cell types in epileptic network activity or identifying
424 circuit components that can control seizure emergence¹⁴¹⁻¹⁴⁵. Notably, optogenetic
425 manipulations can be tested in real-time using closed-loop systems that are able to
426 detect abnormal epileptic activity in real-time, and then trigger light stimulation to inhibit
427 or excite a cell type of interest. Indeed, closed-loop optogenetics identified circuits with
428 promising seizure control capabilities^{120,145-148}. Moreover, closed-loop protocols can
429 also integrate electrical stimulation. In those cases, a stimulation electrode is either
430 implanted in or near the area of interest¹⁴⁹⁻¹⁵², or stimulation is delivered
431 transcranially¹⁵³. Some of the advantages of implementing optogenetics over electrical
432 stimulation are related to the cell type specificity of the stimulation approach.
433 Nevertheless, off-target effects of viral targeting should also be considered and

434 controlled. An additional use of optogenetics is related to the development of new
435 models that take advantage of the cell type specificity of optogenetics. Thus,
436 optokindling^{154,155} has emerged as a complementary approach to the classic kindling
437 paradigm¹⁵⁶ where specific cell types are triggered to test the effects of inducing
438 seizures.

439 Other approaches take advantage of chemogenetic methods¹⁵⁷ for more
440 prolonged manipulation of neuronal populations, to switch on or off a population of
441 interest and determine whether and how they contribute to (physiological, abnormal,
442 or epileptiform) EEG activity¹⁵⁸. A chemogenetic strategy uses a genetically
443 engineered receptor-drug interaction principle and expression of Designer Receptors
444 Activated Only by Designer Drugs (DREADDs) in the tissue of interest^{157,159}. Diverse
445 cell types^{135,160-162} have been inhibited or excited to determine their role in
446 hyperexcitability or seizure initiation. One of the advantages of chemogenetic
447 approaches is that prolonged interventions are possible, as the effects of excitation or
448 inhibition can last for several hours¹⁶³, depending on the dose of the compound used
449 to activate the engineered receptor.

450 Modern *in vivo* imaging techniques combined with EEG recordings have the
451 capacity to provide unprecedented new insights into brain mechanisms in experimental
452 studies¹⁶⁴⁻¹⁶⁶. This area of neuroscience has rapidly expanded due to the development
453 of genetically engineered indicators and novel microscopic techniques for *in vivo*
454 imaging. A large amount of calcium and voltage indicators are currently available,
455 providing the opportunity to record the activity of brain cells with a high cellular and
456 subcellular spatial resolution^{167,168}. Glutamate, GABA, acetylcholine, potassium, ATP,
457 and other types of indicators allow us to study changes in neurotransmission,
458 neuromodulation, and other molecules during epileptiform activity^{169,170}. However, it

459 should be noted that certain calcium indicators can result in aberrant calcium
460 responses, warranting caution when interpreting results¹⁷¹. Genetically engineered
461 voltage indicators¹⁷² represent another approach that offers the ability for one as well
462 as two¹⁷³ photon imaging modalities with relatively minimal toxicity¹⁷⁴. Moreover,
463 repeated imaging can be performed chronically over the weeks or months through a
464 cranial window or using implantable head-fixed microscopes. If necessary, deep
465 structures can be reached using implantable micro-optic fibers. Changes in neuronal
466 or glial activity can thus be monitored over long periods of time. Long-term changes in
467 cellular activity and morphology can be correlated with electrographic changes during
468 various stages of epileptogenesis or disease progression. Such methods are not
469 currently possible to be implemented in humans. However, future epilepsy research
470 will effectively utilize these techniques to describe the mechanisms of epilepsy with
471 high precision and resolution that we currently could not achieve by using traditional
472 approaches or analogous recordings in humans.

473 Overall, given the limitations of each approach, optogenetic, chemogenetics,
474 and *in vivo* imaging studies have greatly contributed to our understanding of circuits
475 and mechanisms involved in epilepsies. However, further refinement may be
476 necessary to overcome issues related to toxicity and off-target effects. For example,
477 relatively simple modifications involving titration of injected virus volume or the use of
478 an alternative promoter could represent effective strategies to address issues related
479 to toxicity^{171,175}. With regards to chemogenetics, the use of alternative ligands¹⁷⁶ and
480 the use of lower doses¹⁷⁷ represent approaches to mitigate off-target effects.

481 **5. Advanced EEG signal analysis**

482 The EEG can be assessed visually by experts or, in some applications, audibly
483 after the conversion of EEG signals to sounds. An advantage of visual assessment by
484 experts is that this is based on principles agreed upon by expert clinical
485 neurophysiologists after decades of EEG studies performed with standardized
486 methods. Even though the agreement level in inter-rater interpretations is not 100%, it
487 provides sufficient power to guide the clinical management of patients or recognize
488 ambiguous EEG signals. Despite its widespread use to study cerebral activity in
489 epilepsy research, it is recognized that the information gleaned from visual inspection
490 can be limited. This limitation arises due to several factors. Firstly, EEG signals are
491 complex, reflecting intricate neural processes involving many different frequencies²⁵.
492 Visual interpretation may overlook subtle patterns, the interaction of such patterns, or
493 nuances that analytical techniques can capture and quantify more effectively.
494 Additionally, human interpretation is subjective, time-consuming, and prone to biases,
495 leading to inconsistencies in findings. Although visual assessment is time-consuming
496 and requires expertise, it still represents the traditional approach to analyzing EEG.
497 The principles of EEG interpretation and CDE criteria can be instrumental in EEG data
498 collection and reporting.

499 Advancements in computer technology and signal processing have enabled the
500 development of sophisticated algorithms for EEG analysis, offering a more
501 comprehensive understanding of brain activity¹⁷⁸⁻¹⁸¹. Automated methods can detect
502 patterns, anomalies, and correlations that may evade human observation. For
503 instance, automatic approaches with machine learning algorithms can process vast
504 amounts of EEG data, identifying subtle changes with high accuracy¹⁸². However,

505 cautious use, including training and validation of such automated approaches in EEG
506 reading by EEG experts, is needed to ascertain the accuracy and biological relevance
507 of data extracted in this manner. Thus, visual assessment remains a valuable tool in
508 EEG analysis. However, integration of validated automated techniques to enhance
509 diagnostic accuracy and provide more comprehensive insights into brain function and
510 dysfunction is needed.

511 Several tools are published that provide open-source platforms for EEG
512 analyses¹⁸³⁻¹⁸⁵. One example is Brainstorm, an open-source application to analyze
513 various brain recordings such as magnetoencephalography (MEG), EEG, near-
514 infrared spectroscopy, ECoG, depth electrodes, and multiunit electrophysiology
515 (<https://neuroimage.usc.edu/brainstorm/>)¹⁸⁶. *EEGLAB* is another example for
516 processing continuous and event-related EEG, MEG, and other electrophysiological
517 data¹⁸⁷. It integrates independent component analysis (ICA), time-frequency analysis,
518 artifact rejection, event-related statistics, and various visualization modes for both
519 averaged and single-trial data (<https://sccn.ucsd.edu/eeglab/index.php>). MNE is an
520 open-source Python package dedicated to exploring, visualizing, and analyzing
521 neurophysiological data, including the ones stated above¹⁸⁸. Other analytical tools can
522 be used for visualizing multimodal datasets containing electrophysiological and
523 behavioral data^{189,190}. In addition, there are several open-access toolboxes that can be
524 used to analyze epileptiform activity and HFOs, such as RippleLab¹⁹¹, HFOApp¹⁹², or
525 PyHFO¹⁹³. Future developments are warranted to allow analyses with minimal cost
526 and comparison of those analyses between different labs using the same open-access
527 tools.

528 Classification of the different EEG patterns has been traditionally based on
529 examining characteristics such as their spectral content, morphology, source, state or

530 event dependency and reactivity, as well as the age of appearance⁶. Extended signal
531 analyses have helped to increase information yield and have provided additional
532 insights into the functional network organization. Measures of synchronization, cross-
533 frequency coupling, mutual information, and non-linear interactions have permitted an
534 understanding of the underlying neuronal and network dynamics¹⁹⁴⁻¹⁹⁸. Unbiased
535 machine learning and data science tools have revealed a large variety of EEG
536 signatures, which can be explained by different activity inputs and brain-wide
537 dynamics^{199,200}. These works have demonstrated that latent EEG information can be
538 exploited to derive clinically relevant biomarkers^{201,202}. The problem with many of these
539 approaches, however, is difficulty in understanding how they base their classificatory
540 power. To ease interpretability, some of these studies have used high-dimensional
541 analysis of the convolutional kernel features²⁰³⁻²⁰⁵ or recurrent neural networks²⁰⁶ to
542 understand what these algorithms recognize as an event.

543 Application of advanced analytical tools and signal processing techniques
544 requires experts with a deep knowledge of mathematics, physics, engineering,
545 computational science, bioinformatics, or complex system dynamics who have the
546 experience to extract relevant data and provide appropriate interpretations. It is
547 important to stress that the use of advanced EEG tools in less experienced hands or
548 even those with experience may lead to mis- or over-interpretation of EEG data. We
549 recommend caution and consultation with the tools' developers to identify common
550 pitfalls and possible sources of variation in data interpretation. Nevertheless, basic
551 EEG analysis became more accessible to a broader research community through the
552 availability of a wide range of online courses or highly didactic material for non-
553 experts^{11,207}, interdisciplinary collaboration, or facilitation of programming skills in
554 MATLAB, Python, or R code with tools like ChatGPT.

555 **6. Challenges associated with EEG and ways to** 556 **address them**

557 Despite EEG having become a sophisticated tool to study epileptic brains, it still
558 has a myriad of limitations. Firstly, it has spatial limitations. Even with many implanted
559 electrodes or multielectrode arrays, the activity is recorded from multiple but spatially
560 limited brain areas and does not cover the whole brain. Moreover, volume conduction
561 can represent an issue when EEG activities are being localized from adjacent
562 electrodes implanted in small rodents like mice or rodent pups. Current-source density
563 analysis represents a powerful tool to overcome volume conduction issues and identify
564 the true origin of the recorded signals^{25,208}. EEG and LFP recordings largely rely on
565 the difference of potentials between the recording area and the area where the
566 reference electrode is placed, as an absolute electrical reference is absent. Thus,
567 signal interpretation can be challenging as it may be limited to the reference montage
568 being used.

569 Animal EEG is an invasive procedure requiring surgery and electrode
570 implantation directly over the cortex or into the brain. As with any surgical procedure,
571 there are risks of surgical complications or confounders that need to be considered,
572 but they are currently required due to the lack of reliable but less invasive alternatives
573 to recording EEGs in experimental animals. The challenges in recording continuous
574 EEG for extended periods of time (weeks to months) in developing animals represent
575 a challenge for research exploring developmental or early-onset epilepsies due to the
576 growing skull and the need for maternal care of developing animals.

577 Artifacts and EEG interpretations represent persisting and essential limitations
578 of EEG recording⁶. Although it seems that recording EEG in rodents is a relatively

579 straightforward proposition, EEG interpretation is quite a challenging issue. There are
580 many ways that the method can provide information that doesn't even originate in the
581 brain but is still misinterpreted, and there are many reports of seizure patterns that are
582 contested and not broadly accepted¹²². In this regard, the TASK1 group of the
583 ILAE/AES Joint Translational Task Force has provided useful reports summarizing the
584 experience in EEG and ECoG studies and interpretation in preclinical studies which
585 can be useful for the reader^{122,178,209-212}.

586 There are several sources of EEG artifacts⁶. Artifacts in EEG recordings can
587 arise from extracerebral sources and are a significant limitation in experimental as well
588 as clinical research. They reduce recording quality, obscure cerebral activity,
589 complicate analysis, and can lead to false interpretations. Every EEG recording,
590 whether clinical or experimental, contains artifacts, which are classified as physiologic
591 or non-physiologic. Physiologic artifacts, like those from animal movement or muscle
592 activity (EMG), are common because they originate from the biological properties of
593 the subject being monitored. Activities such as head scratching, grooming, or eating
594 generate electric fields that can manifest as high-amplitude slow or rhythmic EEG
595 activity, mimicking seizure patterns (**Figure 3**). EMG artifacts, typically arising from
596 muscles near electrodes, can obscure EEG signals and are particularly prevalent
597 during wakefulness. High-quality EEG recordings, with minimal extracerebral
598 interference, are often best obtained during sleep or resting states. Techniques such
599 as bipolar recording, filtering, and shielding can help reduce artifact amplitude. Non-
600 physiologic artifacts originate from the recording setup, including issues with
601 electrodes, cables, and the recording environment. Electrode-related artifacts can
602 result from poor contact, degradation, or disconnection, while environmental factors
603 like the presence of electric devices (e.g., fridges, mobile phones) can introduce noise.

604 Long cables, damaged connections, and mains power supply noise (50-60 Hz) are
605 common non-physiologic artifacts. Proper setup can minimize these artifacts, including
606 shielding, grounding, and cable management. Removing artifacts is critical for accurate
607 EEG analysis. While filtering can remove some high-frequency and slow artifacts, it is
608 not always practical, as it may also eliminate frequencies of cerebral origin. Advanced
609 techniques, such as adaptive artifact rejection and ICA, have been developed to
610 remove specific artifacts while preserving brain signals. In experimental research,
611 ensuring high-quality equipment and minimizing artifact sources is essential for reliable
612 EEG data.

613 Correct interpretation represents the next big issue in rodent EEG recording,
614 especially the interpretation of whether the observed pattern represents a seizure.
615 Although definitions between researchers vary, many definitions in the literature range
616 from “repetitive activity of 5 Hz or greater that is at least double the baseline signal
617 amplitude” or “trains of repetitive spikes of at least 5 seconds.” These definitions are
618 easy to follow and automate for quantifying seizures, but validation by experts is
619 needed alongside video records to exclude the possibility that the observed pattern
620 relates to artifactual events. Similarities between artifacts and epileptiform activity also
621 represent a major challenge, even for sophisticated automatic seizure or epileptiform
622 activity detectors. Therefore, it is essential that the investigator verifies that the pattern
623 of interest is not an artifact and uses appropriate controls as a comparison. The issue
624 of an appropriate control is important in light of the many transgenic animals now
625 available, as the test animal may have an EEG pattern that is not seen in the control
626 “parent” line that is rhythmic or “spikey” but not a seizure.

627 One of the issues for those less familiar with EEG is what an EEG represents,
628 especially from intracranial and intracerebral recordings. There is often the sense that

629 we are observing brain activity at a near-microscopic level, which we are likely not^{6,26}.
630 EEG signals are primarily generated by post-synaptic potentials on a specific subset
631 of neurons, notably the apical dendrites of pyramidal cells in the cortex or the
632 hippocampus. These extracellular field potentials are best observed when many
633 neurons are synchronously oriented in the same direction, creating what are known as
634 open field potentials, visible from outside their immediate source. Most of this EEG
635 activity originates from thalamic input to these pyramidal cells. In contrast, recording
636 activity from regions with less aligned dendrites, like the thalamus or amygdala,
637 requires the electrode to be within the structure, as these non-laminar fields, known as
638 closed fields, do not project externally.

639 When interpreting EEG data, it's crucial to recognize these limitations. The
640 signals primarily reflect activity from specific neuron types and regions, while significant
641 neuronal activities, especially from local interneurons, may not be captured²¹³. This
642 understanding is essential in avoiding overinterpretation of EEG data, particularly in
643 epilepsy research. Despite its usefulness, the tool has inherent limitations that must be
644 considered for accurate analysis.

645 **7. Beyond the EEG: perspectives and future**

646 **directions**

647 New toolboxes of advanced EEG recording devices enable the examination of
648 brain activity from individual neurons to large-scale brain-wide networks (**Table 1**). In
649 addition, recent developments using graphene-based arrays permit recording both unit
650 activity, LFP, and DC potentials at unprecedented levels, thus expanding the range of

651 EEG frequencies to be analyzed²¹⁴⁻²¹⁷. Automatic detection of prototypical EEG
652 patterns such as cortical spindles, interictal spikes, and short-lived HFOs have paved
653 the way for their utilization in clinical practice²¹⁸⁻²²². More recently, new strategies that
654 leverage machine learning and data science tools have proved transformative for the
655 analysis of EEG. Detection of interictal spikes has benefited from the application of
656 unsupervised data-driven classification with decision trees, support vector machines,
657 and other criteria without relying on a priori definitions^{223,224}. Artificial neural networks
658 such as convolutional or recurrent neural networks have permitted supervised training
659 for the identification of generically defined oscillations, such as SPW-Rs in the
660 rodent^{205,225} and primate brain¹⁸⁵ or predicting seizure patterns²⁰⁶.

661 Other approaches that do not involve the use of video-EEG are also useful in
662 epilepsy research. One approach uses machine learning-based behavioral
663 phenotyping of mice²²⁶ to determine hidden behavioral patterns and their evolution
664 during epileptogenesis as well as the response to anti-seizure medications. Such an
665 approach has the advantage of monitoring several behavioral signs, which can be
666 mined and used for fast and automated drug screening in the context of epilepsy.
667 Another approach involves the assessment of regional blood flow using functional
668 ultrasound imaging techniques to allow an understanding of the relationship between
669 regional cerebral blood volume (CBV) changes and graphene-based
670 electrophysiological recordings of epileptic activity²²⁷. The advantage of this approach
671 is that unlike functional magnetic resonance imaging, which permits an indirect
672 measurement of blood flow, concurrent electrophysiological recordings are not
673 influenced by magnetic fields. This work has demonstrated that CBV alterations
674 precede seizures and that imaging of blood flow could be a surrogate biomarker to be
675 incorporated in seizure detection algorithms.

676 Undoubtedly, the EEG has played an essential role in understanding the
677 mechanisms of epilepsy in the last century. A large number of different ictal and
678 interictal epileptiform activities were identified in EEG, which, nowadays, represent
679 gold standard markers that help to diagnose epilepsy, define the epileptic syndromes,
680 and localize epileptic tissue clinically and experimentally. Multiple seizure onset
681 patterns were recognized^{43,66,228}, and now we better understand their candidate
682 mechanisms as well as the mechanisms of various forms of interictal activities. The
683 era of EEG is not over but rather the opposite. We expect that EEG recording
684 technology will significantly expand in the near future. New research techniques such
685 as *in vivo* imaging, genetic control of neuronal activity, and multichannel recordings will
686 bring innovative data about the pathogenesis of epilepsy, but they will always be
687 interpreted with respect to simultaneously recorded EEG to allow for informed
688 interpretations. Technological advances bring new and more sophisticated
689 electrophysiological approaches to record EEG, LFP, and cell activity across multiple
690 temporal, spatial, and frequency scales to provide much more compelling information
691 about the complex nature of epileptic processes. Future methods of EEG analysis
692 implementing AI will increase the information yield obtained from EEG recordings and
693 may become even more robust against artifacts. Recently, we have observed the
694 expansion of *in vitro* techniques (cell cultures or organoids) to study epilepsy.
695 Unfortunately, these techniques can not sufficiently grasp the entire complexity and
696 connectivity of the whole rodent or human brain. Circadian rhythms, sleep, long-term
697 seizure risk fluctuation, and complex network interactions within the whole-brain
698 connectome may be challenging to model and studied using isolated brain tissue.
699 Animal EEG still has a strong position in contemporary epilepsy research, and we
700 predict that this position will not change soon.

701 **Acknowledgments**

702 Premysl Jiruska is a member of the Epilepsy Research Centre Prague (EpiReC)
703 consortium.

704

705 **Funding**

706 CPL is supported by the National Institute on Aging R21AG086880 and an NYU
707 FACES Pilot Research Grant. This study was also supported by grants of the Czech
708 Science Foundation (21-17564S), the Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic (NU21-
709 08-00533), the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (EU –
710 Next Generation EU: LX22NPO5107), ERDF-Project Brain dynamics
711 (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004643), Medical Research Council UK (MR/X004317/1),
712 Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) (under Grant Number 20/FFP-P/8613 (Frontier for
713 the Future project award) and Grant Number 16/RC/3948) and the Charles University
714 project EXCITE (UNCE24/MED/021). CURE Epilepsy Cameron Boyce Foundation
715 Taking Flight Award by the Citizens United for Research in Epilepsy, doing business
716 as CURE Epilepsy, SFI under Grant Number 21/RC/10294 and co-funded under the
717 European Regional Development Fund and by FutureNeuro industry partners to CRR.
718 Fundación La Caixa (LCF/PR/HR21/52410030 and LCF/PR/HR22/52420005) to
719 L.M.P. A.S.G. acknowledges grant support from the NIH (U54 NS100064,
720 R01NS127524), the US Department of Defense (W81XWH-22-1-0510, W81XWH-22-
721 1-0210), an American Epilepsy Society seed grant, a pilot grant from the NICHD (P50
722 HD105352) for the Rose F. Kennedy Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities
723 Research Center, the Heffer Family and the Segal Family Foundations, and the Abbe

724 Goldstein/Joshua Lurie and Laurie Marsh/Dan Levitz families. SB acknowledges grant
725 support from the National Brain Appeal (NBA), Dravet Syndrome Foundation (DSF),
726 and the Italian Ministry of Health and Tuscany Region (grant code RF-2021-12372804,
727 2023-2026). MM acknowledges grant support from the Investissements d’Avenir-
728 Laboratory of Excellence *Ion Channel Science and Therapeutics* (LabEx ICST ANR-
729 11-LABX-0015-01) and University Côte d’Azur (IDEX Jedi ANR-15-IDEX-01).

730 **Conflicts of interest**

731 CPL, MOC, MdC, MM, SB, CRR and PJ have no conflicts of interest related to the
732 manuscript topic. A.S.G. is the Editor-in-Chief of *Epilepsia Open* and associate editor
733 of *Neurobiology of Disease* and receives royalties from Elsevier, Wolters Kluwer, and
734 MedLink for publications but has no conflicts of interest associated with this article.

735

736 **Figure legends**

737 **Figure 1.** Spatiotemporal properties of experimental EEG. EEG recorded at high
738 sampling frequency can explore cerebral activities and processes operating at
739 millisecond or even sub-millisecond time scales. Therefore, we can study fast
740 processes like high-frequency oscillations, interictal discharges, seizure onset, fast
741 propagation, and synchrony. EEG can explore “slow” phenomena operating at the
742 scales of seconds, minutes, or hours, like seizures, spreading depolarization, or DC
743 shifts. On the contrary, long-term EEG recording is valuable for studying processes
744 like circadian rhythms, epilepsy rhythms, epileptogenesis, disease progression,

745 seizure remission, or response to the treatment. The ability of EEG to simultaneously
746 record fast and slow processes is instrumental in studying the long-term profile of fast
747 activities like interictal epileptiform activity or high-frequency oscillations. EEG
748 recording ranging from single to multiple electrodes can provide spatial information
749 from single-cell activity to a whole brain recording from multiple brain structures. The
750 contemporary state-of-the-art techniques of EEG recording can provide an enormous
751 amount of information about epileptic brain dynamics (a gray area).

752

753 **Figure 2.** EEG recording in animals can be combined with other research methods
754 and technologies. EEG can be combined with a variety of *in vivo* structural and
755 functional imaging techniques including a head-fixed microscope. Apart from brain
756 electrical activity, other physiological parameters like electrocardiogram or respiration
757 activity can be recorded simultaneously with EEG. The technological advances
758 contribute to the improvement of EEG recording techniques including new electrode
759 types and new materials. Modern rechargeable telemetric devices allow for
760 multichannel recordings for unlimited periods of time. EEG is effectively combined with
761 other research tools like chemogenetics or optogenetics to dissect the network activity
762 with cellular specificity.

763

764 **Figure 3.** Examples of EEG artifacts from animal activity. **A.** Movement artifact. Based
765 on a review of simultaneously recorded videos, the rat was quiet and then started
766 moving around the cage. The pattern fits the often-used criteria for calling an EEG
767 pattern a seizure: At least five seconds of repetitive activity that is at least twice the
768 amplitude of baseline EEG. **B.** Head-scratching artifact. A prevalent pattern that also

769 fits the above criteria and which shows a pattern of evolution over time. As mentioned
 770 above, artifact as the source of the EEG change was confirmed by simultaneous video
 771 recording.

772 Figures

773

774 **Figure 1.** Spatiotemporal properties of experimental EEG. EEG recorded at high
 775 sampling frequency can explore cerebral activities and processes operating at
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 779 scales of seconds, minutes, or hours, like seizures, spreading depolarization, or DC
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799 Created with BioRender.com.

800

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805 amplitude of baseline EEG. **B.** Head-scratching artifact. A prevalent pattern that also
806 fits the above criteria and which shows a pattern of evolution over time. As mentioned
807 above, artifact as the source of the EEG change was confirmed by simultaneous video
808 recording.

809 **Tables**

810 **Table 1.** Advanced electrophysiological methods directly applied to the study of the
 811 human brain activity *in vivo*.

Probe design	Description	Types of signals	Reference
Laminar arrays (Ulbert)	Multi-electrode (24-48 channels) closely spaced arrays (25 μm steps) along a single polyimide penetrating shank (up to 1 mm)	LFP, CSD, and unit activity with laminar resolution	²²⁹
Grid-like arrays (Utah)	2-dimensional planar (usually 4 x 4 mm) silicon-based multi-electrode (currently 96-1024 channels) arrays located at the tip (e.g. 400 μm)	LFP and unit activity at a fixed depth in the cortex. Since the original design, many configurations have been developed, including 3D recordings (Utah slanted design)	²³⁰
Neuropixels	Ultra-dense (20 μm spacing) fully integrated linear array (384-user selectable channels) distributed along a penetrating shank (10 mm long)	LFP and units all along the probe shank with improved recording stability	²³¹
NeuroGrid	Thin-film-based (10x10 μm) closely spaced array (30 μm) of organic polymer electrodes (256 channels)	Surface electrocorticographic and LFP signals and units	²³²

CSD = Current source density; LFP = Local field potential

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